

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D2.3 TWINNING SCHEMES REPORT 31/12/2025

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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D2.3 TWINNING SCHEMES REPORT

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Abstract	This report presents the Twinning schemes implemented within the CATALISI project as part of the <i>Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach</i> acceleration service. Through nine in-person visits and 22 exchange interactions, the Twinning mechanism supported targeted peer learning among Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The exchanges enabled staff members from HEIs to observe and compare concrete institutional practices (e.g. policies, structures, organisational models, governance models, workflows, etc) across key intervention areas. The findings highlight that the Twinning schemes is an effective and replicable approach to strengthen institutional capacity and support long-term transformation within the European Research Area.
Keywords	Knowledge sharing; mutual learning; Twinning exchanges; Institutional transformation; Higher Education Institutions; peer-to-peer learning; European Research Area; institutional

	cooperation; transformational pathways; acceleration services; capacity building.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the design, implementation and outcomes of the **Twinning schemes** carried out within the CATALISI project under Task 2.4 – *Exchange the knowledge through Twinning schemes*, as part of the broader acceleration service “*Reinforce Human Capital: Capacity Building & Outreach*”. The Twinning mechanism was conceived as a targeted, practice-oriented peer-learning activity to support institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), complementing broader mutual learning formats such as the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops.

Across the project, **nine Twinning visits** were organised, resulting in **22 staff exchanges** involving the seven CATALISI implementing HEIs. These peer-to-peer exchanges enabled staff from different institutional levels to engage in focused, in-person learning experiences, observe concrete institutional practices on site and exchange experiences on priority intervention areas identified in their Transformational Pathways. These areas included, among others, Open Science, research ethics and integrity, research assessment, public engagement and research culture.

The analysis presented in this deliverable draws on Twinning reports produced by both host and visiting institutions, complemented by qualitative reflections and debriefings. The evidence confirms that the Twinning mechanism generated **significant added value** for institutional learning and change. Visiting institutions benefited from hands-on insights into mature practices and clearer identification of internal gaps and priorities, while host institutions gained structured feedback and opportunities for critical self-reflection. In many cases, the exchanges produced concrete takeaways that directly informed the refinement of Transformation Actions.

The results of the Twinning schemes clearly demonstrate the **effectiveness and replicability** of targeted peer-to-peer exchanges as an acceleration service for institutional transformation in the field of Research and Innovation (R&I). The analysis highlights how Twinning exchanges contribute to strengthening institutional capacity, clarifying priorities, and fostering ownership of change processes, while also reinforcing collaboration among HEIs across Europe. Key success factors included clear learning objectives, prior matchmaking between institutional needs and expertise, multi-level participation and the opportunity to combine focused thematic agendas with interactive and informal dialogue.

At the same time, the experience underscored areas for further enhancement, including the need to ensure sufficient time for deeper engagement, broaden the involvement of external actors where appropriate and embed Twinning schemes more structurally within institutional strategies supported by dedicated resources. While in-person exchanges were consistently identified as the most impactful format, the findings also suggest that elements of the Twinning methodology could be meaningfully adapted to online or hybrid settings when physical mobility is not feasible.

Overall, the Twinning schemes, implemented alongside the MML workshops within the “*Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach*” acceleration service, proved to be a powerful lever for institutional learning and change. Beyond facilitating peer exchange, they contributed to embedding a culture of peer learning, strategic collaboration and continuous improvement within and between participating HEIs, supporting the advancement of more resilient, adaptive and interconnected institutions within the European Research Area.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	9
1.1.	BACKGROUND AND AIM OF CATALISI.....	9
1.2.	AIM AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	10
2.	ORGANISATION AND APPROACH OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES.....	12
2.1.	CONNECTION AND COORDINATION WITH RELATED ACTIVITIES.....	12
2.2.	CONTENT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES.....	12
2.2.1.	FORMAT.....	14
2.2.2.	PLANNING AND PREPARATION WORK.....	15
3.	OVERVIEW OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES.....	19
3.1.	TWINNING ON <i>OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES AND PRACTICES</i> AT KTU.....	19
3.1.1.	Details of the visit.....	19
3.1.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	19
3.1.3.	Activities performed.....	19
3.1.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation.....	20
3.2.	TWINNING ON <i>RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY</i> AT AUMC.....	21
3.2.1.	Details of the visit.....	21
3.2.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	21
3.2.3.	Activities performed.....	22
3.2.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation.....	22
3.3.	TWINNING ON <i>REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND ENGAGEMENT WITH LOCAL ECOSYSTEM</i> AT LUISS.....	23
3.3.1.	Details of the visit.....	23
3.3.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	24
3.3.3.	Activities performed.....	24
3.3.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation.....	25
3.4.	TWINNING ON <i>PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND RESEARCH CAREERS</i> AT UCC.....	26
3.4.1.	Details of the event.....	26
3.4.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	26
3.4.3.	Activities performed.....	27
3.4.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation.....	27
3.5.	TWINNING ON <i>OPEN SCIENCE, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH</i> AT KTU.....	28
3.5.1.	Details of the visit.....	28
3.5.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	29
3.5.3.	Activities performed.....	29
3.5.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation.....	30
3.6.	TWINNING ON <i>SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH</i> AT AUTH.....	31
3.6.1.	Details of the visit.....	31
3.6.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit.....	31
3.6.3.	Activities performed.....	31

3.6.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation	32
3.7.	TWINNING ON <i>OPEN ACCESS PRACTICES</i> AT UJI.....	33
3.7.1.	Details of the visit	33
3.7.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit	33
3.7.3.	Activities performed.....	33
3.7.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation	34
3.8.	TWINNING ON <i>PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT TO SOLVE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</i> AT UG.....	35
3.8.1.	Details of the visit	35
3.8.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit	35
3.8.3.	Activities performed.....	36
3.8.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation	36
3.9.	TWINNING ON <i>OPEN SCIENCE AND RECOGNITION OF QUALIFICATION AND RESEARCH CAREERS</i> AT AUMC	37
3.9.1.	Details of the visit	37
3.9.2.	Thematic focus and Aim of the visit	38
3.9.3.	Activities performed.....	38
3.9.4.	Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation	39
4.	KEY RESULTS OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES IMPLEMENTATION AS ACCELERATION SERVICE: DATA AND REFLECTIONS	40
4.1.	QUANTITATIVE INSIGHTS	40
4.1.1.	Participants.....	40
4.1.2.	Topics covered.....	43
4.1.3.	Evaluation.....	44
4.2.	QUALITATIVE OUTCOMES AND PERSPECTIVES	44
4.2.1.	Success factors of the Twinning mechanism	45
4.2.2.	Benefits for HEIs' transformational pathways	45
4.2.3.	Limitations and Areas of improvements	46
5.	CONCLUSIONS.....	47
6.	REFERENCES.....	48

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1 - MATRIX OF THE 22 TWINNING EXCHANGES CARRIED OUT</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Figure 2 – MATCHMAKING EXERCISE DURING THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOP, CATALISI GENERAL ASSEMBLY, 18TH JANUARY 2024</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>Figure 3 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY KTU</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Figure 4 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY AUMC.....</i>	<i>22</i>
<i>Figure 5 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY LUISS.....</i>	<i>25</i>
<i>Figure 6 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UCC.....</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>Figure 7 – SECOND TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY KTU</i>	<i>30</i>

Figure 8 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UJI.....34

Figure 9 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UG..... 36

Figure 10 – SECOND TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY AUMC..... 39

Figure 11 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE NUMBER OF TRAINERS AND TRAINEES INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS 41

Figure 12 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE POSITION HELD BY THE TRAINERS INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS..... 41

Figure 13 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE POSITION HELD BY THE TRAINEES INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS.....42

Figure 14 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE MOST RECURRING TOPICS ADDRESSED IN THE TWINNING VISITS.....43

Figure 15 – WORDCLOUD REPRESENTING PARTICIPANTS' FEEDBACK TO THE TWINNING VISITS.....44

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – OVERVIEW OF THE TWINNING VISITS..... 13

ABBREVIATIONS

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
AUMC	Amsterdam UMC
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
CoP	Community of Practice
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EY	Ernst & Young
F6S	F6S Network Ireland Limited
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
LL	Living Labs
Luiss	Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
QH	Quadruple-Helix
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
UCC	University College Cork
UG	University of Gdansk
UJI	Universitat Jaume I
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND AIM OF CATALISI

Institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) has emerged as a key strategy to address the evolving challenges of Research and Innovation (R&I) and to steer the profound changes affecting science, technology and innovation ecosystems. As highlighted by the European Commission¹, transforming Higher Education Institutions is essential to ensure that R&I systems remain aligned with societal values, needs and expectations, while strengthening cooperation with citizens, industry and civil society. This reflects a broader policy effort within the European Research Area (ERA)² and the Higher Education Transformation Agenda³ to reinforce the role of universities as central actors in shaping Europe's scientific, economic and social future.

In this context, CATALISI contributes to the EC's objective of spreading and embedding institutional transformation across HEIs by supporting seven universities in the design, implementation and consolidation of tailored strategies for change. The project helps HEIs to develop individual pathways for institutional transformation, combining short-term achievements with medium- and long-term structural reforms meant to persist beyond the project's lifetime. These pathways, co-designed with internal and external stakeholders, provide the roadmap through which HEIs can enhance their governance models, strengthen openness and inclusiveness, and improve their capacity to respond to societal challenges.

To support this complex process, CATALISI has identified three domains of intervention (Research careers and Talent support, Research Modus Operandi and Sustainable Research and Education), each articulated into specific intervention areas where institutional change is deemed necessary. In parallel, the project has developed a set of seven Acceleration Services designed to facilitate, accompany and accelerate transformation: the **Living Lab**, providing the overarching framework for co-creation and participatory governance; the **Design Lab for transformational pathways**, supporting strategy building and agenda-setting; the **Counselling service**, offering tailored coaching and mentoring; the **Capacity building & Outreach programme**, which includes the Learning Hub, Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops, and Twinning schemes; a **Predictive study on skills anticipation**, to support HEIs in rethinking investments in education and training; the **Catalyst Hub**, facilitating access to funding and partnerships; a **Community of Practice (CoP)**, bringing together experts and stakeholders on institutional change from different European countries.

Through these services, HEIs are not only supported in implementing institutional change within their own organisations but are also progressively empowered to become service providers themselves, contributing expertise to their peers across Europe.

Among the acceleration services, the **Capacity building & outreach programme** plays a pivotal role, as it structures opportunities for learning, exchange and cross-fertilisation. Within this programme, knowledge sharing and mutual learning represent essential enablers for institutional transformation. MML workshops, Learning Hub activities and Twinning schemes provide concrete opportunities for HEIs to share experiences, gather practical insights, and translate good practices into actionable steps within their own transformation pathways. These activities help implementers⁴ refine their strategies, address challenges, and co-create

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628>.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628>.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf.

⁴ CATALISI model is built upon two blocks: on one side, four facilitators (APRE, EY, ENoLL, F6S) that are responsible for accelerating and facilitating the transformational pathways of HEIs through the provision of acceleration services. On the other

innovative solutions with other HEIs and relevant stakeholders from the quadruple helix (academia, public authorities, civil society and industry).

Overall, CATALISI seeks to strengthen HEIs' capacity to innovate their governance, operations and strategic vision in line with ERA priorities, thereby enabling universities to better cooperate, contribute to European universities alliances, and respond more effectively to societal, scientific and economic challenges.

1.2. AIM AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The main goal of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive report on the Twinning schemes implemented under *Task 2.4 – Exchange the knowledge through Twinning schemes*, within the broader framework of the Capacity building & Outreach Acceleration service. In line with the objectives of WP2, the report highlights how peer-to-peer staff exchanges have facilitated the transfer, consolidation and practical application of knowledge and innovative transformation practices, enabling CATALISI implementers to learn from one another and to observe first-hand how institutional transformations have been carried out in different organisational contexts.

Beyond offering a concrete overview of the Twinning activities carried out by the seven implementing HEIs, the deliverable also aims to assess the effectiveness of the Twinning mechanism as an instrument for mutual learning and institutional change. To this end, this report evaluates how far the Twinning schemes have contributed to the overall CATALISI objectives, and how they have supported the advancement of each HEI's transformational pathway.

Building on the methodological foundation and implementation framework set out in *D2.1 – Knowledge Sharing and Mutual Learning Plan*⁵, the deliverable presents achievements, strengths, challenges and lessons learned arising from the **22 Twinning exchanges** organised throughout the project. It also offers analytical insights into how the Twinning scheme has operated not only as a project activity, but as an acceleration mechanism capable of reinforcing capacities, fostering cross-institutional collaboration, and creating favourable conditions for sustainable and meaningful institutional transformation across the three CATALISI domains.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 – Introduction** outlines the background and the rationale of the CATALISI project and explains the role of the Twinning schemes within the broader set of acceleration services.
- **Chapter 2 – Organisation and methodology of the Twinning schemes** describes how the Twinning activities build upon the activities carried out in other WPs, outlines the matchmaking analysis facilitated by APRE and explains the design and preparation phases leading to each exchange.
- **Chapter 3 – Overview of the Twinning visits** provides a detailed summary of each Twinning, including their thematic focus, activities carried out and key takeaways for host and visiting institutions.

side there are the implementers who are the HEIs participating in the project and that are pursuing institutional transformations, namely Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), University Jaume I of Castellon (UJI), Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (Luiss), Gdansk University (UG), University College Cork (UCC), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) and Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC).

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393609>

- **Chapter 4 – Key results of the Twinning implementation: data and reflection** presents an analysis of the quantitative and qualitative evidence collected across the exchanges, assessing the overall effectiveness of the Twinning schemes and their overall contribution to HEIs' institutional change.
- **Chapter 5 – Conclusions** summarises the main findings of the report and provides considerations for sustaining, institutionalise and potentially scaling up the Twinning approach beyond the CATALISI project.

2. ORGANISATION AND APPROACH OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES

2.1. CONNECTION AND COORDINATION WITH RELATED ACTIVITIES

The Twinning schemes implemented under *Task 2.4 – Exchange the knowledge through Twinning schemes* are closely interconnected with several preparatory and complementary activities carried out in other CATALISI Work Packages (WPs). As already highlighted in *D2.2 – Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report*⁶, these preparatory activities laid the conceptual and operational foundations upon which the Twinning exchanges were designed, structured and executed. Although the Twinning and Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops differ in format and objectives, they are part of the same Acceleration service and build upon the same knowledge base, methodological inputs and strategic tools developed earlier in the project.

A first major contribution comes from WP1, particularly *Task 1.1 – Setting up the CATALISI Acting-Living Labs* and *Task 1.2 – Living Labs: exploration stage*, which played a pivotal role in mapping the initial conditions for institutional transformation in each implementing HEI. Through a series of collaborative workshops facilitated by ENoLL, these tasks supported the identification of transformation priorities, relevant intervention areas and systemic barriers that could hinder or enable change in each HEI. The preliminary exploration of stakeholder ecosystems performed in WP1 also proved essential for the Twinning schemes, as it enabled each HEI to identify internal actors and organisational units whose involvement would be strategic during the peer-learning visits.

Further foundations were provided by *Task 3.2 – Design Lab for transformational pathways: strategy and agenda setting*, where EY introduced and adapted a Reflection Tool inspired by the TIME4CS⁷ methodology. This tool guided implementers in outlining their personalised transformational pathways, defining their strategic objectives and specifying the actions needed to achieve short-, medium-, and long-term institutional changes. By clarifying each HEI's vision, priorities and challenges, the Reflection Tool directly informed the matchmaking process of Task 2.4, helping identify which HEIs were better positioned to act as hosts or visitors within specific intervention areas.

In addition to these contributions, the methodological basis for the Twinning schemes was shaped by *D2.1 – Knowledge Sharing and Mutual Learning Plan*, which established the formats and expected outcomes of the project's Capacity Building & Outreach activities. The plan emphasised the importance of matching needs and expertise across HEIs, involving executive and managerial staff, and ensuring that each exchange contributes to the advancement of the implementers' transformational pathways.

2.2. CONTENT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES

The Twinning visits collectively covered all three domains and several intervention areas of institutional transformation identified in CATALISI⁸, allowing for flexibility based on

⁶ D2.2 – Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report has been submitted to the EC in April 2025 and, together with D2.3 – Twinning schemes Report, will be subject to evaluation during the final reporting period.

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7022933>

⁸ For reasons of conciseness and to avoid duplication, the full list of the 14 CATALISI Intervention Areas is not repeated here; it is extensively described in **D2.2 – Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report** (Chapter 1 – Introduction). They are: recognition of qualifications & research careers; reform of research assessment; digitisation of higher education sector; supporting talent circulation/mobility; accurately addressing lifelong learning; strengthening of human capital; gender equality and inclusiveness; mainstreaming of Open Science; public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges;

implementers' evolving needs, and enabled implementers to benefit from targeted peer-to-peer learning opportunities. Table 1 below provides a synthetic overview of host institutions, visiting partners and thematic focus of each exchange, while Figure 1 provides an overview of the 22 exchange interactions realised.

TABLE 1 – OVERVIEW OF THE TWINNING VISITS

TWINNING HOST	VISITING INSTITUTION	TOPIC/INTERVENTION AREA	DATE
KTU	AUMC	Mainstreaming of Open Science	10/05/2024
AUMC	UG, UJI	Research Ethics and Integrity	11/06/2024
Luiss	AUTH, KTU, UJI	Research assessment; engagement with local ecosystem (Third Mission)	18/10/2024
UCC	Luiss, AUMC, KTU, UJI	Public engagement and research careers	13/11/2024
KTU	UCC, UJI, UG, AUTH, Luiss	Mainstreaming of Open Science, public engagement and sustainability in research	09/12/2024
AUTH	UCC, UG	Sustainability in research	23/01/2025
UJI	AUMC, Luiss	Mainstreaming of Open Science; reform of research assessment	03/04/2025
UG	KTU, AUTH	Public engagement	10/04/2025
AUMC	UCC, Luiss, AUTH	Open Science; recognition of qualifications and research careers	15-16/05/2025

FIGURE 1 - MATRIX OF THE 22 TWINNING EXCHANGES CARRIED OUT

2.2.1. FORMAT

While complementary to the MML workshops, the Twinning schemes differ in that they are based on focused staff exchanges, allowing implementers to observe first-hand how specific institutional transformation practices are implemented in other organisations.

Each Twinning visit was conceived as a **one or two-day in-person exchange**, hosted by an HEI considered more experienced in each domain or intervention area. The format typically included different type of activities such as:

- **Introductory sessions** presenting the host institution's governance, transformation priorities and ongoing institutional change initiatives.
- **Peer-learning and mentoring sessions**, where the hosting HEI demonstrated concrete tools, processes, practices and solutions implemented within the intervention area of expertise.
- **Interactive discussions and problem-solving activities**, enabling visiting HEIs to ask questions, analyse critical success factors, and explore how practices could be adapted to their own context.
- **Meetings with key internal stakeholders**, including executive staff, middle managers, researchers, administrative units and service providers involved in institutional transformation.
- **Concluding reflections**, supporting visiting HEIs in identifying actionable takeaways, lessons learned and next steps for their transformational pathways.

Each HEI participated in a **minimum of three Twinning exchanges (as visiting institution) for a total of 22 exchanges**, and some HEIs acted as hosts depending on their expertise and maturity level in specific intervention areas.

In order to evaluate and assess the effectiveness of the Twinning schemes, the format also incorporated the use of the **"Twinning Reporting Template"** (see Appendix C), ensuring systematic documentation of each exchange, including agenda, participant profiles, activities carried out, key learnings, challenges encountered, and relevance to the HEIs' transformational pathways.

2.2.2. PLANNING AND PREPARATION WORK

The planning and preparation of the Twinning schemes was coordinated by **APRE**, as facilitator of this activity, in continuous collaboration with each of the implementers.

APRE guided the entire process, from the early conceptualisation to the finalisation of host–visitor pairs and agendas, ensuring coherence with the objectives of Task 2.4 and with the broader Capacity Building & Outreach Acceleration Service. The preparatory work required a customised and careful alignment of transformation needs and expertise and was articulated across three phases: **before**, **during** and **after** the Twinning exchanges.

BEFORE THE TWINNING EXCHANGES

1. **Identification of needs and expertise:** the preparatory phase began in November 2023, with a comprehensive analysis of the transformation needs and priorities emerging from WP1 and WP3. In this context, and in collaboration with EY as WP3 leader, APRE supported the distribution of a dedicated **questionnaire** to all implementing HEIs. This questionnaire served multiple purposes:
 - identifying the areas, topics and intervention areas where each HEI required additional support or guidance, including those most relevant for the *Counselling* acceleration service (facilitated by EY);
 - mapping internal expertise, allowing implementers to indicate in which transformation topics their institution felt confident and experienced, and in which areas they needed peer learning or direct support;
 - detecting imbalances and complementarities across the consortium, highlighting which HEIs were better positioned to act as "hosts/trainers" for specific thematic areas, and which were better suited to participate as "visitors/trainees".

The results provided a picture of strengths, gaps and needs, complementing insights gathered through the Acting Living Labs and the first drafts of the transformational pathways. Together, these elements formed the analytical basis for the Twinning schemes. They enabled APRE to construct an **evidence-based matchmaking framework**, aligning the support needs of less experienced institutions with the demonstrated expertise of potential hosting HEIs, ensuring that each Twinning exchange would be relevant, targeted and impactful.

2. **Co-creation workshop to validate matchmaking results:** a decisive moment in the planning process was the co-creation workshop held during the first CATALISI General Assembly in January 2024. During this session:
 - APRE presented the initial matchmaking results developed based on the questionnaire's responses;
 - Implementers collectively validated, refined and prioritised the thematic clusters;

- HEIs identified which of their intervention areas were suitable for hosting and which required learning as visitors;
- HEIs identified and discussed possible dates for the Twinning exchanges to be performed.

The workshop contributed to openly discuss expectations, learning objectives and practical implementation details, and to establish the foundations for the final Twinning calendar. This participatory exercise also ensured that the final matchmaking reflected **actual institutional needs** and not only the initial assumptions outlined in D2.1.

Matchmaking Results		HUMAN CAPITAL				RESEARCH MODUS OPERANDI				FINANCE					
		RECOGNITION OF QUALIFICATIONS & RESEARCH CAREERS	REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT	DIGITIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR	SUPPORTING TALENT CIRCULATION/MOBILITY	ADDRESSING LIFELONG LEARNING	STRENGTHENING OF HUMAN CAPITAL	GENDER EQUALITY & INCLUSIVENESS	MAINSTREAMING OF LIFE SCIENCE AND DIGITIZATION OF RESEARCH	PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT WITH AND OUTREACH TO SOCIETY TO SOLVE SOCIAL CHALLENGES	REINFORCING THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES IN LOCAL INNOVATION SYSTEMS	SHARING OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES AND CAPACITIES	SUSTAINABILITY IN EDUCATION	SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH	SUSTAINABILITY IN CAMPUS OPERATIONS
EXPERTISE OFFERED		UCC (expertise from different projects)	UCC (CoARA National Chapter for Ireland)	UCC (assessment systems based on metrics on research careers)	AUTH (Massive Open Online Courses – MOOCs to enhance educational accessibility and flexibility)	VUMC (good practices in RCI in annual evaluation of researchers)	RTU (advanced digital infrastructure and digitalization of study courses)	UCC (internal system of evaluation that we have adopted at LIUSC (called VIRI))		RTU (strong competence and possibility of training in open data, open science, open data archive)	UCC (Campus Engage National Framework, UNICABER Framework)	UCC (Citizen Science experiences)	VUMC (Support in grant applications and expertise in ethics, Data Management, Open Science)	UG (good practices, training, transformation processes)	
SUPPORT NEEDED		AUTH (development of a formal mechanism to recognize qualifications gained in Living Labs)	UG (tool to conduct surveys within faculties - the potential of research services to the external environment)	UCC (need of a new assessment model that combines qualitative and quantitative criteria)	VUMC (willingness to improve the ethical structure of research, especially with regard to the way ethics committees operate)	VUMC (gap between policy and practice with regard to responsible conduct of research)	UCC (need to increase the funds available to LIUSC as a host institution for projects of research excellence (MSCA and ERC), focusing in particular on updating the internal policies (including incentives))	RTU (need to develop a dedicated program for Alumni addressing their needs and priorities -> how to learn about this?)	UG (development of a system (i.e. traffic light meter) to measure and evaluate the community's progress in gender equality)	VUMC (development of a system (i.e. traffic light meter) to measure and evaluate the community's progress in Public engagement process)	LIUSC (to increase the adoption of OS practices among the faculty, starting from OA, and develop tools/instrument)	LIUSC (to increase the quality of our public engagement activities (and how to best incentivise the faculty to take part in them) - covered with...)	UCC (back of sufficient budget allocation, absence of a database for managing IP and collaborative projects)	RTU (fostering interdisciplinary cooperation system on existing competences, peer to peer experiences)	UG (diagnosis of the potential for sustainable campus management)

FIGURE 2 – MATCHMAKING EXERCISE DURING THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOP, CATALISI GENERAL ASSEMBLY, 18TH JANUARY 2024

3. **Finalisation of Twinning visits' timeline:** following the first General Assembly, APRE carried out bilateral consultations with the HEIs to consolidate the Twinning plan and adjust it to: institutional calendars; availability of executive and managerial staff; logistical feasibility and travel considerations.

As a result, the preliminary timeline outlined in D2.1 was **revised and improved**, leading to a more realistic and flexible implementation plan aligned with the practical and thematic needs of each HEI.

For economic and environmental reasons, the Twinning visits were sometimes combined with the organisation of the onsite MML workshops, allowing both events to take place onsite in a single timeframe. Moreover, when a specific intervention area and destination were of interest to more than one HEI, the Twinning visits were grouped together, enabling multiple visiting HEIs to attend the same host institution simultaneously.

4. **Development of the agenda and definition of activities:** once the calendar exchanges and the host and visiting implementers were confirmed, APRE supported each host institution in designing the agenda and structure of the visits. This included the organisation of dedicated online meetings with both host and visiting institutions aimed at:
 - defining learning objectives and expected outcomes of the Twinning exchange to be performed;
 - preparing a detailed agenda covering diverse activities, such as presentations, mentoring sessions, stakeholder meetings and on-site visits of relevant infrastructures (if any);
 - identifying the appropriate internal units and personnel to involve as "trainers" (e.g. executive staff, middle managers, service offices, researchers) based on the Twinning's focus;
 - ensuring that activities remained focused on concrete practices relevant to the selected intervention area and to the needs of the visiting HEIs.
5. **Preparation of documentation and reporting tools:** APRE, as facilitator and task leader of this activity, provided each host and visiting HEI with the Twinning Reporting template (see Appendix C) with the aim to documenting agendas, participants and activities prior to the visit as well as capturing insights, lessons learned and recommendations after the twinning exchange with the overall aim of assessing the exchange's relevance as an acceleration service for their transformational pathways.

DURING THE TWINNING EXCHANGES

1. **Coordination and facilitation support:** throughout the visits, APRE remained available to support host and visiting institutions in managing unforeseen needs, ensuring adherence to the learning objectives set during the preparatory phase. Although onsite facilitation was not required (differently from the MML workshops), APRE took part in some Twinning exchanges as external observer and monitored progress, collected intermediate feedback and ensured coherence with the methodology defined in D2.1.

AFTER THE TWINNING EXCHANGES

1. **Follow-up, evaluation and reporting:** after each Twinning exchange, APRE guided implementers through the reporting process to assess the contribution of Twinning schemes to the HEIs' capacity building and to the progress of institutional transformation through the Reporting Template earlier provided.

2. **Results analysis:** APRE conducted a cross-case analysis of all Twinning reports to identify:
 - Recurrent challenges and success factors;
 - Opportunities for replicability and scalability;
 - Recommendations for future twinning activities beyond the lifetime of CATALISI.

3. OVERVIEW OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES

In the following sections, a detailed overview of each Twinning Visit is provided, together with the main points discussed and the summary of key messages.

3.1. TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES AND PRACTICES AT KTU

3.1.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC)
DATE	10/05/2024
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Mainstreaming of Open Science
PARTICIPANTS	12, including trainers from KTU and staff members from AUMC.

3.1.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning visit was designed to share KTU's experience in developing and implementing Open Science practices and to provide a concrete view of how supporting infrastructures and governance arrangements can foster institutional change in this field. The main objectives were to:

- present KTU's approach to open educational resources and open data (e-library, data centre, national data archive);
- discuss research ethics practices and their integration with Open Science policies;
- showcase the infrastructure for Open Science applications and its role in enabling interdisciplinary collaboration.

For AUMC, the visit offered an opportunity to benchmark its own Open Science and research integrity strategies against those of a technical university in another national context, and to explore how physical and organisational infrastructures can support responsible research practices.

3.1.3. Activities performed

The programme combined **thematic discussions** and **onsite visits**. The exchange opened with a session at the **Data Centre** on "Open Science Policy and Data", where participants were introduced to KTU's open data practices, including the **LiDA data archive for social sciences**, and discussed incentives and recognition mechanisms for data deposition in researchers' career assessment. This was followed by a meeting with members of the **University Research Ethics Committee**, focusing on how Open Science is implemented at KTU and in Lithuania more broadly, and how ethics governance structures have been shaped drawing

on experiences from European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU) partners. In the afternoon, the delegation visited the **KTU Campus Library** to explore services for open publications and citizen science, and then the **M-Lab prototyping centre**, where discussions centred on how physical spaces and shared infrastructure can facilitate interdisciplinary cooperation and innovation. Throughout the day, the agenda allowed for interactive exchanges, questions and reflection on transferability to the visitors' institutional contexts.

FIGURE 3 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY KTU

3.1.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The Twinning produced clear and tangible benefits for both the host and the visiting institutions, directly contributing to the refinement and advancement of their respective transformational pathways.

For KTU, the visit was an opportunity to receive structured feedback from AUMC on its Open Science and ethics arrangements, and to reflect on how these practices compare with those of a leading medical research institution, thereby informing further development of KTU's own Open Science structures and ethics governance. In particular, the exchange allowed KTU to:

- receive structured feedback on its Open Science, ethics and data governance arrangements;
- better understand how ethics and Open Science are operationalised in a biomedical context, and how these practices differ from or converge with Lithuanian context;
- reflect on strengths and remaining gaps in its Open Science implementation model, particularly regarding researcher incentives and policy–practice alignment;
- confirm the maturity and robustness of its current Open Science infrastructure, reinforcing internal confidence and strategic direction.

For AUMC, the exchange was relevant and directly useful for the advancement of its transformational pathway. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- new insights into open data infrastructures,

- insights into how dedicated units (e.g. library, Data Centre, Ethics Committees) collaborate to enable Open Science;
- inspiration from KTU's practical integration of data deposition into research workflows, informing potential reforms in their own systems;
- recognition of how physical spaces, such as the M-Lab, can foster interdisciplinary collaboration and citizen engagement;
- better understanding of how ethics governance interacts with Open Science and data management, informing AUMC's own strategic reflections.

Both partners highlighted the value of combining **discussion-based sessions with onsite observation of infrastructure** and underlined the potential to build on this first exchange to develop more **concrete joint outputs** (e.g. shared reflections or position papers on institutional transformation and Open Science). A general observation from both sides was that Twinning, even in an intensive one-day format, can act as a **qualitative accelerator** of institutional change by exposing teams to alternative models and prompting strategic reflection on how to adapt them at home.

3.2. TWINNING ON RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY AT AUMC

3.2.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Amsterdam UMC (AUMC)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Universitat Jaume I (UJI); University of Gdansk (UG)
DATE	11/06/2024
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Recognition of qualifications and research careers; Reform of Research assessment
PARTICIPANTS	15, including trainers from AUMC and staff members from UJI and UG.

3.2.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

This Twinning centred on how to strengthen research ethics and research integrity systems and policies, an area where VUMC is highly advanced and in which UJI and UG are carrying out institutional changes.

The exchange aimed to:

- provide UJI and UG with a practical view of governance structures, procedures and culture around research integrity in Dutch institutions;
- explore the functioning of Research Ethics Committees and Academic Integrity Committees, with a focus on their professionalism, mandate, and resourcing;

- discuss emerging topics in research ethics, supporting visiting institutions in assessing their own readiness and gaps;
- promote reflection on how faculties, rectorates and central offices share responsibility for ensuring compliance and how policies can be developed.

For both UJI and UG, the visit addressed direct needs related to ethics governance, staff capability-building and compliance with European research integrity frameworks.

3.2.3. Activities performed

The programme combined thematic discussions with experts designed to give visiting institutions a comprehensive understanding of AUMC's approach to research ethics and integrity.

The visit opened with a **workshop on research ethics governance**, where experts from AUMC and the *National Ethics Council for Social and Behavioural Sciences* introduced the visitors to Dutch research ethics' procedures, emerging ethical challenges, and the professionalisation of committee work. A short campus tour followed, providing contextual understanding of how ethics and integrity services are embedded within the institution.

In the afternoon, the trainees participated in a **session on Academic Integrity Committees**, led by coordinators of the *Netherlands Research Integrity Network* (NRIN), which explored approaches for handling questionable research practices, prevention mechanisms, and shared responsibilities across faculties and central offices. The final workshop focused on a **training for research integrity**, showcasing educational materials and tools developed at AUMC, including resources from *The Embassy of Good Science*, and discussing how training frameworks can be adapted to different institutional contexts.

Across all sessions, the program enabled interactive dialogue, comparison of national systems, and reflection on how VUMC's practices could be transferred or adapted to the visiting institutions' settings.

FIGURE 4 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY AUMC

3.2.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

Although the exchange focused primarily on knowledge transfer from AUMC to UJI and UG, the visit also generated valuable insights for the host, strengthening its own reflection on research ethics and integrity governance.

For AUMC, the Twinning offered an opportunity to receive external perspectives on its well-established ethics and integrity structures and to reflect on how these systems compare with those of other European universities. In particular, the exchange allowed AUMC to:

- compare its ethics and integrity procedures against those in Spain and Poland, identifying points of convergence and divergence;
- reflect on how responsibilities for ethics oversight are distributed across faculties, rectorates and central offices in different governance systems;
- gain insight into how other institutions interpret and implement European research integrity frameworks;
- provide examples of its own system, which may serve as models for peers.

For UJI and UG, the exchange was highly relevant and directly useful for the advancement of their institutional transformation pathways, especially in strengthening ethics governance, developing integrity structures and improving compliance processes. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- deeper understanding of how Dutch Research Ethics Committees (RECs) operate, including procedural workflows, professionalism, and decision-making criteria;
- insight into how dedicated bodies such as national ethics councils, academic integrity committees and networks collaborate within a multi-level governance system;
- practical ideas for improving their own committee structures, including clearer role distribution, dedicated training and professional recognition for committee members;
- recognition of the need to strengthen institutional support for ethics and integrity, ensuring that responsibilities are shared and properly coordinated across organisational levels;
- a clearer view of how to develop or revise internal procedures to ensure alignment with European standards and evolving research practices.

All institutions emphasised the value of discussing real cases and internal procedures directly with practitioners, noting that the opportunity to compare Dutch, Spanish and Polish approaches offered particularly rich insights. A shared reflection across partners was that Twinning represents a **powerful catalyst for institutional change**, helping universities rapidly identify realistic improvements and understand how mature systems function through direct dialogue with experienced peers.

3.3. TWINNING ON REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND ENGAGEMENT WITH LOCAL ECOSYSTEM AT LUISS

3.3.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali (Luiss)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH); Kaunas University of Technology (KTU); Universitat Jaume I (UJI).
DATE	18/10/2024

DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Reform of Research assessment; engagement with local ecosystem.
PARTICIPANTS	11, including trainers from Luiss and staff members from AUTH, KTU and UJI.

3.3.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

This Twinning focused on how Luiss has designed and operationalised its internal research assessment system, how it interfaces with national evaluation procedures and how it connects to the university's broader strategy for external engagement and "Third Mission" activities.

The aim of the exchange was to:

- present the structure, rationale and implementation of the internal research assessment system as a tool to promote high-quality research;
- discuss how Luiss manages research outputs, datasets and Third Mission contributions, including connections with local businesses and societal actors;
- illustrate how different internal units and offices (e.g. Research & Third Mission Office, Library, X.ITE Research Centre) work together to support evaluation and engagement;
- provide AUTH, KTU and UJI with models and practices they could adapt in the context of their own institutional reforms.

For visiting HEIs, the Twinning addressed specific needs, especially in relation to internal assessment systems, productivity measures, and mechanisms for promoting impactful research.

3.3.3. Activities performed

The programme combined thematic presentations, guided discussions and onsite visits. The day opened with a comprehensive introduction to the internal research evaluation system, delivered by LUISS' Research and Third Mission Office. Library staff then presented how the library contributes to the internal research evaluation system, including the management of Iris, LUISS' platform for tracking publications, and its role in supporting the national research evaluation procedure.

A dedicated session followed on the use of indicators for different **internal assessment** purposes, which led to an open discussion among all universities on the challenges and opportunities of research evaluation reform.

The second thematic block centred on **external engagement** and the local ecosystem. A presentation at the Luiss X.ITE Research Centre illustrated how research groups collaborate with businesses and external partners, with a focus on commissioned research and valorisation strategies. This was complemented by an interactive discussion on Third Mission activities and their integration with research assessment practices.

In the afternoon, participants moved to the Villa Blanc campus for a guided tour, followed by a visit to the **LUISS Library**, where participants explored spaces, tools and services supporting research visibility, dissemination and engagement.

Throughout the day, exchanges were highly interactive, allowing visiting institutions to ask detailed questions, compare internal procedures and assess how LUISS' model could be adapted to different institutional contexts.

FIGURE 5 - TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY LUISS

3.3.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The visit was extremely useful for both host and visiting institutions with clear and tangible benefits.

For Luiss, the Twinning offered an opportunity to present its internal evaluation system and Third Mission activities to peers and to reflect on how these models are perceived externally. In particular, the exchange allowed LUISS to:

- gather valuable external perspectives on the functioning and transparency of its internal research evaluation system;
- understand how assessment procedures and engagement strategies are approached in Greek, Lithuanian and Spanish universities, highlighting convergences and contextual differences;
- refine its thinking on how to further integrate research evaluation with Third Mission and local ecosystem engagement;
- experience the importance of fostering direct dialogue between administrative and technical staff and academics from different institutions as part of institutional transformation.

For AUTH, KTU and UJI, the Twinning was highly relevant and directly useful for the advancement of their transformation pathways, especially regarding research assessment reform and strategies for strengthening engagement with societal actors. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- clearer understanding of how an internal research evaluation system can be structured, monitored and communicated across the institution;
- insights into the role of digital tools, such as institutional repositories, in supporting evaluation and transparency;
- practical ideas for strengthening links between research performance, external engagement and societal impact;

- recognition of the value of transparent and user-friendly evaluation systems, particularly in supporting academic motivation and institutional cohesion;

All institutions emphasised the value of discussing real procedures and internal workflows directly with LUISS' administrative and academic staff. Visiting HEIs particularly appreciated the opportunity to have a thorough look at the internal research assessment system and to understand its operational implications.

3.4. TWINNING ON *PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND RESEARCH CAREERS* AT UCC

3.4.1. Details of the event

HOST INSTITUTION	University College Cork (UCC)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Amsterdam UMC (AUMC); Kaunas University of Technology (KTU); Universitat Jaume I (UJI); Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali (Luiss, online participation)
DATE	13/11/2024
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve societal challenges; reform of research assessment.
PARTICIPANTS	11, including trainers from UCC and staff members from AUMC, KTU, UJI and Luiss (online).

3.4.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning hosted by UCC focused on how public engagement and research careers can be strategically embedded into institutional structures, research culture and support services. The visit aimed to:

- present UCC's mature system for public and societal engagement, including organisational structures, governance models and impact practices;
- illustrate how research career development is supported through dedicated teams, training pathways and recognition mechanisms;
- showcase how impact assessment is integrated into research support services;
- offer visiting HEIs practical insights into how to strengthen engagement strategies and develop coherent support models for researchers.

The Twinning addressed explicit needs emerging from the visitors' transformational pathways, particularly regarding capacity-building for engagement, career support systems and the creation of effective research services.

3.4.3. Activities performed

The programme combined thematic dialogues, interactive discussions and institutional reflections.

The day began with an exploration of **UCC's approach to values, integrity and open science**, focusing on how responsible research principles are embedded into the everyday practices of academic staff. Participants discussed the structural and cultural conditions needed to sustain these principles over time.

The second thematic block centred on **researchers' engagement with communities**, highlighting UCC's experience in fostering relationships with societal stakeholders and encouraging researchers to integrate engagement into their research activities. UCC shared examples of how community partnerships support trust-building, enhance research relevance and strengthen responsible research practices.

A third discussion focused on **ethics and integrity governance**, examining how ethics review processes operate at UCC and how institutional structures promote a positive research culture.

Throughout the visit, participants also worked on advancing the **joint UCC-VUMC-UJI Research Integrity & Research Culture Survey**, which aims to support culture-change initiatives across CATALISI institutions.

The agenda remained highly interactive, giving all partners space to compare national systems, discuss organisational challenges and explore how UCC's practices could be adapted within their own contexts.

FIGURE 6 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UCC

3.4.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

Although the exchange focused primarily on knowledge transfer from UCC to the visiting institutions, the Twinning also provided valuable opportunities for UCC to reflect on its own practices and gather external perspectives on its integrity, ethics and public engagement approaches.

For UCC, the Twinning enabled the institution to:

- consider how its approaches to integrity, ethics and open science are perceived by external peers;
- reflect on how to further strengthen the visibility and coherence of its Third Mission and engagement practices;
- understand how other institutions connect societal engagement with research culture and responsible research;
- consolidate collaboration with AUMC and UJI on shared tools for monitoring research culture.

For AUMC, UJI and KTU, the Twinning significantly supported their transformation pathways, particularly regarding ethics governance, Research integrity training and engagement strategies. Key learning outcomes included:

- clearer understanding of how integrity, ethics and open science principles can shape the overall research culture of an institution;
- insights into how engagement with communities can enhance responsible research and reinforce trust in academic institutions;
- concrete ideas for strengthening support structures that encourage researchers to participate in societal engagement;
- recognition of the importance of linking ethics and integrity frameworks with ongoing engagement efforts;
- confirmation that embedding engagement within internal transformation strategies is essential to building resilient and open research ecosystems.

All institutions emphasised the value of discussing real examples of engagement practices and exploring how they intersect with integrity and open science.

3.5. TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH AT KTU

3.5.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	University College Cork (UCC); Universitat Jaume I (UJI); Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali (Luiss); University of Gdansk (UG); Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH).
DATE	09/12/2024
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Mainstreaming of Open Science; Public engagement; Sustainability in research.
PARTICIPANTS	19, including trainers from KTU and staff members from UCC, AUTH, UG, UJI and Luiss (online).

3.5.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

In alignment to the previous Twinning exchange hosted by KTU, this visit focused on **mainstreaming Open Science** within institutional structures, governance and daily research practice.

The main aims of the visit were to:

- present KTU's approach to **Open Science policy**, FAIR data management and digital research services;
- introduce visitors to KTU's **research ethics governance**, including committee processes and staff roles;
- demonstrate how Open Science connects with **societal engagement**, public access to data, and accessible research communication;
- offer a space for visitors to compare practices, raise questions and reflect on the transferability of KTU's model.

3.5.3. Activities performed

The Twinning visit at KTU was structured around three thematic areas: sustainability in research, open science and open data, and research ethics and public engagement, providing visiting institutions with a clear overview of how these elements are embedded in KTU's research ecosystem.

The programme opened with a session on **sustainability in research**, during which the KTU's project management system and funding schemes was presented. The discussion focused on long-term approaches to sustaining research initiatives, maintaining collaborations and securing stable support for researchers.

The second part focused on **open science and open data**. Participants were introduced to the Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences (LiDA) and to KTU's practices for data archiving and reuse. Conversations addressed researcher motivation, data stewardship and how data-sharing efforts are acknowledged within KTU's assessment processes and impacts public engagement.

The visit concluded with a session on **open science and research ethics**, through a meeting with the University Research Ethics Committee. Committee members described how Open Science is practiced at KTU and in Lithuania, sharing experiences from KTU and European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU) partners and discussing how ethics governance supports transparent and responsible research.

Across all sessions, visitors were encouraged to raise questions and compare institutional approaches, resulting in a rich exchange of perspectives on the practical implementation of Open Science and ethics.

FIGURE 7 – SECOND TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY KTU

3.5.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The Twinning gave KTU an important opportunity to reflect on the strengths of its own system and to better understand how its Open Science, ethics and data practices are perceived by external peers.

For **KTU**, the Twinning enabled the institution to:

- gain external perspectives on its approach to Open Science, open data and ethical review processes;
- better understand which aspects of its model stood out as strengths for visiting partners;
- reflect on how to improve internal communication on data-sharing incentives and ethics procedures;
- identify areas where strengthened awareness-raising and training could further support research engagement.

For **UCC, UJI, UG, AUTH and LUISS**, the Twinning significantly supported their transformation pathways, particularly in relation to Open Science implementation, data management practices, ethics governance and the integration of these elements into institutional culture. Key learning outcomes included:

- a clearer understanding of how Open Science, ethical review and data stewardship can work as a coherent system rather than as isolated processes;
- practical insights into how a university-level data centre can support FAIR data practices and encourage researchers to deposit and reuse data and how to embed it into the national open science system;
- recognition of the central role of ethics governance in enabling transparent and responsible research;
- concrete ideas for improving institutional communication, training and support structures to strengthen researcher motivation for Open Science;
- a better sense of how public-oriented data practices and ethical openness can reinforce societal engagement and institutional trust.

All institutions valued the opportunity to discuss real procedures with KTU staff and to compare national approaches to Open Science and research ethics. Partners noted that seeing how KTU has operationalised these principles provided practical, transferable examples that can inform their own institutional changes.

3.6. TWINNING ON SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH AT AUTH

3.6.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	University College Cork (UCC); University of Gdansk (UG).
DATE	23/01/2025
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Sustainability in research.
PARTICIPANTS	15, including trainers from AUTH and staff members from UCC and UG.

3.6.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning at AUTH focused on sustainability in research, examining how sustainability principles are integrated into the university's research activities, project development, support structures and institutional policies. The visit also addressed AUTH's approach to Open Science, as well as its participation in European initiatives and networks that support transformation in research practices.

The visit aimed to:

- present AUTH's experience in embedding research sustainability across different faculties and support units;
- discuss how sustainability considerations inform project design, funding decisions and long-term planning;
- illustrate how Open Science practices contribute to transparent and sustainable research environments;
- showcase AUTH's **Living Labs methodology in healthcare and interdisciplinary studies**, highlighting how co-creation, user engagement, and real-world testing contribute to sustainable innovation;
- foster dialogue with UCC and UG on shared challenges such as funding continuity, alignment with institutional strategy and the evolving role of universities in the European Research Area (ERA).

3.6.3. Activities performed

The Twinning consisted of a series of thematic presentations and interactive exchanges.

The visit opened with an institutional introduction outlining **AUTH's structure, research priorities and strategic focus on sustainability**. AUTH staff explained how sustainability is embedded in research governance and how different university units contribute to maintaining and supporting long-term research activity.

A second session explored **AUTH's participation in European networks and initiatives**, highlighting how involvement in international consortia and research programmes supports sustainability objectives, strengthens visibility and fosters capacity building.

Participants then engaged in a presentation on **Open Science practices at AUTH**, which covered institutional policies, ongoing initiatives and the relationship between Open Science and responsible research conduct. A key highlight of the visit was the **presentation of AUTH's expertise in Living Labs methodology in healthcare and interdisciplinary projects**. Through concrete examples, AUTH demonstrated how Living Labs enable sustainable research by integrating end-users, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders into the research and innovation process, supporting real-life testing, iterative development, and long-term societal impact.

3.6.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The Twinning produced clear and tangible benefits for both the host and the visiting institutions, directly contributing to the refinement and advancement of their respective transformational pathways.

For **AUTH**, the visit was an important opportunity to reflect on how its approach to research sustainability and Open Science is perceived by external peers and how these practices compare with those in Ireland and Poland. In particular, the exchange allowed AUTH to:

- receive feedback on its sustainability-related initiatives and on how they are integrated into research processes;
- better understand how other HEIs approach the alignment between sustainability, institutional priorities and research support structures;
- reflect on areas where internal communication and coordination around sustainability could be strengthened;

For **UCC and UG**, the exchange was relevant and directly useful for the advancement of their transformational pathways. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- new insights into how AUTH incorporates sustainability approaches into research structures and support mechanisms;
- In depth showcasing of several Living Lab initiatives by AUTH proved to be very informative in demonstrating how the hosting institution applies and executes the methodology.
- better understanding of how international collaboration and European networks can reinforce institutional capacity for sustainable research;
- practical ideas for improving internal alignment between sustainability priorities, Open Science practices and research management;
- recognition of how sustainability approaches can strengthen long-term planning and research support within their own institutions.

Both partners highlighted the value of discussing AUTH's concrete examples and internal organisation, noting that the opportunity to compare different national and institutional contexts enriched their strategic reflections.

3.7. TWINNING ON OPEN ACCESS PRACTICES AT UJI

3.7.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Universitat Jaume I (UJI)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Amsterdam UMC (AUMC); Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali (Luiss).
DATE	03/04/2025
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Reform of research assessment; mainstreaming of Open Science.
PARTICIPANTS	8, including trainers from UJI and staff members from AUMC and Luiss.

3.7.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning at UJI focused on one core theme central to the institution's transformation agenda: the advancement of **Open Access practices**.

The visit aimed to:

- Present UJI's evolving system for evaluating scientific output and research performance, with special attention to its integration of Open Science principles.
- Deepen the understanding of the ecosystem of Spanish non-commercial Open Access journals, particularly in the social sciences and humanities.
- Illustrate how diamond Open Access can be strengthened, both editorially and institutionally, through sustainable workflows, support structures and governance models.
- Foster dialogue with AUMC and Luiss by sharing institutional strategies for promoting Open Science and Open Access, and by comparing infrastructures and national contexts to assess complementarities and transferable practices.
- Identify common challenges and opportunities for joint action, including the development of shared resources, training initiatives and policy recommendations.

3.7.3. Activities performed

The programme combined a series of presentations, discussions and a visit to UJI's library, all centred on **Open Access** as the main thematic focus of the Twinning.

The visit began with a guided tour of the UJI Library and an informal conversation with the staff responsible for Open Access-related services. This introduction set the scene for the full-day programme, which aimed to explore the current state and future perspectives of Open Access at UJI and in partner institutions.

The formal agenda opened with a session on **the relevance of Open Access in contemporary science**, delivered by the Vice-Rector for Research, Jesús Lancis. This was

followed by presentations from journal editors affiliated with UJI, who shared their experience managing academic journals and discussed both the opportunities and constraints of non-commercial Open Access publishing models.

Subsequent sessions explored the landscape of **Spanish academic journals**, focusing particularly on social sciences, humanities and communication studies. These discussions examined alternative publishing structures beyond commercial models and considered how diamond Open Access could be strengthened.

The afternoon focused on **national and institutional Open Access initiatives**, with contributions from AUMC on Dutch policies and from Luiss on the university's progression toward Open Science. These exchanges offered a comparative perspective that allowed participants to reflect on differences in national frameworks, institutional strategies and resource availability.

Throughout the day, the Twinning fostered open dialogue between UJI, AUMC and LUISS, enabling all partners to explore challenges, exchange good practices and reflect on the transferability of different Open Access models across contexts.

FIGURE 8 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UJI

3.7.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The Twinning produced clear benefits for both the host and the visiting institutions, contributing directly to the advancement of their respective transformational pathways.

For **UJI**, the exchange was especially valuable as it allowed the university to:

- showcase the progress made in its Open Access agenda to both external partners and its internal community;
- reflect on its current institutional strategies and identify areas that require further development;
- better understand differences between national frameworks (Spanish, Dutch, Italian) and how these shape institutional approaches to Open Access;
- gain confirmation of the importance of continuing to support diamond Open Access, reinforced by the Vice-Rector's intention to increase the budget allocated to this area.

For the **visiting institutions**, the Twinning was directly useful for advancing their own transformation efforts in Open Science and research assessment. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- new insights into how UJI supports **non-commercial Open Access publishing** and how editorial activities are organised within the university;

- a clearer understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with different Open Access models across countries;
- practical ideas for enhancing institutional strategies, especially regarding how Open Access is communicated, supported and incentivised;
- recognition of the value of discussing national legislation and policy frameworks to better situate institutional reforms within broader systems.

All partners highlighted the usefulness of speaking directly with UJI staff and journal editors, noting that the comparative discussion across three national settings enriched their strategic reflections. The Twinning served as a constructive space to explore how Open Access principles can be realistically implemented within diverse institutional and regulatory environments, helping all institutions refine their ongoing transformation pathways.

3.8. TWINNING ON PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT TO SOLVE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES AT UG

3.8.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	University of Gdansk (UG)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH); Kaunas University of Technology (KTU).
DATE	10/04/2025
DURATION	1 full day
INTERVENTION AREAS	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve societal challenges.
PARTICIPANTS	11, including trainers from UG and staff members from AUTH and KTU.

3.8.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning focused on how universities can strengthen their **engagement with society** and improve how research is communicated, disseminated and made accessible to broader audiences. The host aimed to demonstrate how public engagement is embedded in UG's structures and activities, and how different units (academic departments, the library, cultural assets, and media platforms) contribute to the university's societal mission.

FIGURE 9 – TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY UG

The visit also explored **Open Science practices**, examining how transparency, openness and outreach can reinforce each other when universities commit to a “university for society” model. A central objective of the Twinning was to foster discussion on practical ways to create inclusive, accessible spaces that enable citizens to interact with scientific knowledge.

3.8.3. Activities performed

The programme combined onsite visits, presentations and hands-on examples of engagement initiatives.

The day opened with an introductory session on public engagement and outreach to society. Participants were shown concrete initiatives through a **guided tour** highlighting UG’s labs, student areas, the Experts Council and other activities designed to address social challenges. The visit illustrated how **community-oriented activities** are integrated into the faculty’s infrastructure and daily operations.

The group then transferred to the main campus, where the second session took place at the University Library. Here, UG presented its **Open Science and society-oriented initiatives**, showcasing library resources, discussing how Open Science practices are implemented, and engaging visitors in a dialogue on challenges and opportunities in strengthening openness and community engagement.

In the afternoon, the visit continued at two **cultural and media spaces** managed by UG: the Mini-Museum of Amber and the University Radio MORS studio. Through these visits, participants explored how universities can use cultural heritage, communication channels and physical spaces to disseminate scientific knowledge to diverse audiences. The session concluded with a discussion on how universities can create open, accessible spaces and promote the idea of a “university for society”.

Throughout the day, the agenda encouraged active dialogue, allowing participants to share institutional experiences and compare different approaches to public engagement and Open Science.

3.8.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The Twinning produced clear and tangible benefits for both the host and the visiting institutions, directly contributing to the advancement of their respective transformational pathways.

For **UG**, the exchange was a valuable opportunity to reflect on how its public engagement and Open Science initiatives are perceived by external peers. In particular, the visit allowed UG to:

- receive feedback on its efforts to connect with society and disseminate research more broadly;
- better understand how universities with different disciplinary profiles and experiences approach public engagement and Open Science;
- reflect on how to strengthen communication and coordination across units involved in societal engagement;
- recognise the value of using existing university spaces (e.g. cultural, academic and media-related) to foster greater openness and visibility.

For the **visiting institutions**, the Twinning provided relevant insights that support their own transformation pathways in public engagement and Open Science. Several important learning outcomes emerged:

- new perspectives on how universities can design spaces and activities to foster community engagement, using diverse formats and infrastructures;
- deeper understanding of how public outreach and Open Science can mutually reinforce each other;
- practical ideas for disseminating research to broad audiences and creating welcoming, accessible spaces for societal interaction;
- recognition of the importance of exchanging real examples and practical experiences to identify concrete actions suitable for their contexts.

Both visiting partners highlighted the value of the hands-on, example-driven format of the Twinning, noting that the combination of presentations, tours and discussions facilitated peer learning.

3.9. TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE AND RECOGNITION OF QUALIFICATION AND RESEARCH CAREERS AT AUMC

3.9.1. Details of the visit

HOST INSTITUTION	Amsterdam UMC (AUMC)
VISITING INSTITUTIONS	University College Cork (UCC); Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali (Luiss).
DATE	15-16/05/2025
DURATION	2 half days
INTERVENTION AREAS	Mainstreaming of Open Science; recognition of qualifications and research careers.

PARTICIPANTS

20, including trainers from AUMC and staff members from UCC and Luiss.

3.9.2. Thematic focus and Aim of the visit

The Twinning was structured around two closely connected themes. **Day 1** focused on the recognition of qualifications and research careers, with particular attention to recognition & rewards policies and initiatives to support a positive research culture. **Day 2** turned to the mainstreaming of Open Science, impact and valorisation, exploring how these dimensions are embedded in institutional strategies, support structures and assessment practices.

The overall aim was to present how AUMC and its partners in Amsterdam address researcher assessment, recognition & rewards, Open Science and research impact in practice, while creating space for UCC and LUISS to share their own approaches and reflect together on challenges, opportunities and possible adaptations within their institutional contexts.

3.9.3. Activities performed

The programme was organised over **two half-day sessions**, allowing time both for structured presentations and in-depth exchanges.

On Day 1, representatives from VU Amsterdam and AUMC presented the **Recognition & Rewards Programme**, followed by a session on initiatives to raise awareness and stimulate a positive research culture. The day concluded with a participatory session where all partners mapped recognition and rewards initiatives and challenges in their own institutions, comparing experiences and identifying shared issues.

On Day 2, the theme shifted to the mainstreaming of **Open Science and research impact and valorisation**. The agenda included presentations on the VU Amsterdam Open Science Programme, the mission and community engagement work of the Center for Research Integrity and Open Science (RIOS), and several research initiatives on Open Science and reproducibility, followed by a roundtable discussion. In the afternoon, participants heard about the **VU Diamond Open Access journal** – Philosophy of AI and institutional approaches to impact and valorisation in the Humanities and Social Sciences, before joining a final roundtable on institutional strategies for research impact and valorisation.

Throughout both days, the Twinning “involved presentations from multiple stakeholders of the host institution (policy advisors, researchers, programme leads, etc.)”, and was deliberately designed to leave “ample time for interaction” between presenters and partners, including exchanges on how research assessment, Open Science, and impact/valorisation procedures are organised at the visiting institutions.

FIGURE 10 – SECOND TWINNING VISIT HOSTED BY AUMC

3.9.4. Key takeaways and contribution to institutional transformation

The exchange was widely considered as **useful and relevant for advancing ongoing transformational pathways**, particularly because it offered participants an in-depth view of how AUMC and VU Amsterdam organise their internal policies, support structures and institutional strategies in these areas.

For **AUMC**, the Twinning provided an opportunity to receive external perspectives on its practices and to better understand the needs, priorities and approaches of partner institutions. In addition, it was useful for AUMC as well, to learn from the invited stakeholders presenting their insights and experiences with regards to topics related to researcher assessment, research culture and open science. The dialogue with UCC and Luiss helped AUMC reflect on how recognition & rewards, Open Science and research assessment are communicated and operationalised in different institutional contexts, offering insights that will be considered as part of future internal developments. AUMC also highlighted the value of having a diverse set of presenters (e.g. policy advisors, programme leads, researchers) who contributed to a multidimensional picture of its own system. The Twinning helped local stakeholders to connect and exchange.

For the **visiting institutions**, the Twinning was described as highly valuable for their transformation pathways. Participants emphasised that the most important learning outcomes included:

- a clearer understanding of how recognition & rewards policies can be structured and promoted within large research organisations;
- exposure to concrete initiatives supporting a positive research culture and responsible research assessment;
- insights into how institutional Open Science strategies are implemented in practice, including training, governance and incentives;
- practical examples of how impact and valorisation can be integrated into support services and assessment procedures.

Both UCC and LUISS underlined that these learnings will directly inform internal reflection and discussions within their organisations, especially regarding the development of

researcher career frameworks, Open Science support and impact and research valorisation strategies.

4. KEY RESULTS OF THE TWINNING SCHEMES IMPLEMENTATION AS ACCELERATION SERVICE: DATA AND REFLECTIONS

4.1. QUANTITATIVE INSIGHTS

In the framework of the CATALISI project, the acceleration service “Reinforce Human Capital: Capacity Building & Outreach” supported the implementers in the organisation of **nine Twinning visits**, which collectively generated **22 exchange interactions**. While the number of visits captures the structure of the activity, the number of exchanges more accurately reflects the scale of participation and the extent of peer-to-peer learning activated across the CATALISI implementers. Each Twinning functioned as a targeted visit designed to facilitate and accelerate institutional transformation through direct knowledge exchange among HEIs, offering a trustworthy and dynamic environment in which implementers could observe practices on-site, receive contextualised feedback and explore concrete approaches to advancing their own Transformational Pathways by learning from peers with greater experience in specific thematic areas.

The quantitative insights presented in the following sections draw on a systematic analysis of the documentation produced throughout the Twinning process, ensuring a comprehensive and evidence-based overview of participation patterns, thematic focus and emerging trends. In particular, the findings are based on:

- The Twinning Reports completed by each host and visiting institution, providing detailed information on participant profiles, agendas, themes addressed and structured feedback and reflections.
- Informal debriefings conducted during or after the visits with implementers, which offered contextual clarification and deeper insight into motivations, expectations and perceived benefits.

This approach enables a robust understanding of how the Twinning mechanism was implemented and how it contributed to institutional learning across the HEIs, ultimately illustrating the added value of the Twinning schemes as a key driver of institutional transformation within the CATALISI framework.

4.1.1. Participants

A total of **122 participants**, including both trainers and trainees, were engaged and took part in the Twinning visits. As illustrated in Figure 11, **trainers** accounted for **62%** of all participants, while **trainees** represented **38%**. This distribution reflects the multi-actor and multi-level nature of the Twinning format: each visit engaged a broad set of institutional actors on the host side, enabling the visiting institutions to interact not only with project team members but also with those directly responsible for specific governance, technical or operational functions.

FIGURE 11 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE NUMBER OF TRAINERS AND TRAINEES INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS

The roles held by **trainers** (Figure 12) reveal a strong representation of **technical and administrative staff** (27), followed by **professors and researchers** (21) and **middle-management staff** (17). A smaller but significant number of **top-management** representatives (10) also acted as trainers⁹.

FIGURE 12 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE POSITION HELD BY THE TRAINERS INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS

This composition is particularly meaningful for three reasons:

1. **Operational depth of the exchanges:** the prevalence of technical and administrative profiles among trainers indicates that Twinning visits offered access to the practical mechanisms through which institutional practices, such as Open Science, research ethics, data governance or public engagement, are implemented on a day-to-day basis. This aligns with the Twinning logic of enabling visitors to observe how things work in practice.
2. **Integration of academic perspectives:** the strong involvement of professors and researchers ensured that discussions were grounded both in institutional strategies and in research practices. Academic trainers often acted as "translators" between policy frameworks and disciplinary realities.
3. **Strategic anchoring:** the participation of top-management actors (vice-rectors, directors, heads of units) strengthened the legitimacy and internal coherence of the

⁹ Top-management bodies include profiles such as Rectors, Vice-rectors, Deans, Vice-deans, Directors of Research; Middle-management bodies include for example Head of offices, experts, research coordinators; Technical and administrative staff include operational positions such as personnel working in research services and offices, libraries, data centre.

Twinning visits, allowing visitors to understand the broader strategic direction underpinning the showcased practices.

The distribution of roles among **trainees** (Figure 13) shows a balanced presence of **professors/researchers** (16), **technical and administrative staff** (10) and **middle-management personnel** (10), with contributions from **top-management** representatives (8) and **project managers** (2)¹⁰.

FIGURE 13 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE POSITION HELD BY THE TRAINEES INVOLVED IN THE TWINNING VISITS

This reflects key dynamics:

1. **Multi-level knowledge transfer:** representatives of visiting institutions were not limited to CATALISI project teams but included individuals positioned at various levels of the institutional hierarchy. This composition increased the likelihood that observed practices could be meaningfully adapted and transferred internally after the end of the Twinning exchanges.
2. **Complementarity with trainers' profiles:** the overlap in categories (e.g., professors learning from professors; managers learning from managers) enabled exchanges that were both peer-based and role-specific, strengthening the relevance and uptake of insights.
3. **Strategic exposure:** the presence of top-management representatives among trainees indicates a clear effort by visiting institutions to embed Twinning outcomes into broader institutional reforms.

Although the Twinning format was primarily designed for peer exchange among CATALISI implementers, several visits involved the participation of external experts, advisory bodies, or professionals beyond the internal project teams. Their contribution added value in at least two ways:

- **Contextualisation:** external speakers (e.g., ethics committee members not involved in CATALISI, editors of scientific journals, Open Science specialists, community engagement officers) provided insights that positioned institutional practices within broader national and European landscapes.

¹⁰ Top-management bodies include profiles such as Rectors, Vice-rectors, Deans, Vice-deans, Directors of Research; Middle-management bodies include for example Head of offices, experts, research coordinators; Technical and administrative staff include operational positions such as personnel working in research services and offices, libraries, data centre.

- **External perspective:** their presence supported a more objective reading of institutional strengths and challenges, enriching the quality of feedback available to visiting institutions.

This combined picture indicates that the Twinning schemes activated a rich ecosystem of competences, involving individuals responsible for strategy, governance, operational implementation and academic leadership. This diversity reflects the complexity of institutional transformation processes: from CATALISI we learn that meaningful change requires the alignment of vision and strategic embedding (top-management), design (middle-management), implementation (technical and administrative staff) and cultural uptake (professors/researchers).

The Twinning schemes succeeded in bringing these different layers together, creating an institutional environment where knowledge exchange could be both strategically relevant and operationally actionable.

4.1.2. Topics covered

The distribution of topics addressed across the Twinning visits closely reflects the Transformational Pathways and priority areas for institutional change identified by the implementers within the CATALISI project. As illustrated in Figure 14, Open Science, Research Assessment (including ethics and integrity), and Public Engagement emerge as the most frequently addressed themes. This high recurrence aligns with the needs analysis conducted during the initial phases of the project and with the **matchmaking exercise**, which highlighted these areas as those where HEIs expressed the strongest demand for targeted support and peer learning.

FIGURE 14 – CHART ILLUSTRATING THE MOST RECURRING TOPICS ADDRESSED IN THE TWINNING VISITS

Open Science practices, responsible research assessment and public engagement with society and local ecosystems represent cross-cutting dimensions of institutional transformation that influence multiple organisational layers, from governance and incentives to research culture, infrastructures and the development of human capital. Their recurrent appearance across the Twinning visits indicates a shared recognition among implementers of the **structural changes required to align with broader European agendas such as ERA, CoARA and the evolving Open Science policy landscape.**

The presence of **Sustainability in research** and **Recognition of qualifications and research careers**, although less frequent in numerical terms, remains highly significant. These topics

tend to surface in HEIs that are addressing systemic questions around long-term research capacity, talent development or the coherence of internal governance structures.

Overall, the topic frequency analysis confirms two key insights. First, the Twinning scheme succeeded in engaging implementers around the areas that had emerged as the most critical for institutional change within CATALISI (a strong indication that the matchmaking process effectively connected HEIs based on complementary needs, expertise and maturity levels). Second, the convergence of thematic focus across universities suggests a collective movement toward shared strategic priorities, reinforcing the added value of the Twinning mechanism as a driver of mutual learning and prioritisation of intervention areas in line with the ERA within the consortium.

4.1.3. Evaluation

The feedback provided by both host and visiting institutions in the Twinning reports shows a consistently positive evaluation of the Twinning exchanges. As illustrated in the word cloud below (Figure 15), participants repeatedly described the Twinning visits as **relevant, inspiring, well organised** and characterised by strong **engagement and meaningful peer learning**. Institutions valued the opportunity to observe concrete practices, exchange experiences with colleagues facing similar challenges and gain concrete insights directly connected to their own Transformational Pathways.

FIGURE 15 – WORDCLOUD REPRESENTING PARTICIPANTS' FEEDBACK TO THE TWINNING VISITS

Words such as *inspiration*, *practice*, *sharing*, *motivation*, and *clarity* reflect the perceived usefulness of the exchanges, not only for deepening understanding of specific thematic areas but also for stimulating reflection, strengthening networking, and informing ongoing institutional change efforts. Overall, the evaluation confirms that the Twinning mechanism effectively supported knowledge transfer, fostered collaborative learning, and reinforced the collective capacity of CATALISI implementers to advance their institutional transformation processes.

4.2. QUALITATIVE OUTCOMES AND PERSPECTIVES

The Twinning mechanism within CATALISI demonstrated a strong capacity to accelerate knowledge transfer and institutional learning and to support implementers in advancing specific aspects of their Transformational Pathways, as also shown by the results of the Survey on Impact Assessment conducted by UCC (WP4). Across the nine visits, the Twinning format offered a structured yet flexible environment for dialogue, peer learning, comparison of institutional approaches and the collection of concrete insights relevant to R&I governance. The analysis of all Twinning reports and the debriefings with implementers reveal several qualitative insights that shed light on *how* and *why* the Twinning mechanism supports

institutional transformation and which conditions are most conducive to effective knowledge exchange.

4.2.1. Success factors of the Twinning mechanism

Several transversal success factors emerged across the Twinning visits, helping to explain and better understand why this mechanism proved highly effective as part of the broader acceleration service "Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach":

- **Multi-level participation:** as highlighted in the previous section, twinning visits brought together top management, middle management, technical/administrative staff and academic actors. This multi-level composition created a learning environment, where visitors could understand not only the strategic rationale behind an approach but also its operational implementation and cultural underpinnings.
- **Access to real practice and operational insights:** a real added-value of the Twinning mechanism was the opportunity to observe institutional practices on-site: data infrastructures, ethics workflows, Open Science services, editorial processes, engagement facilities, etc. This opportunity to have a closer look at concrete practice made the learning more actionable and impactful.
- **Thematic focus combined with clear objectives and flexible, interactive format:** while each Twinning visit was designed based on a clear thematic focus, one of the strengths of the CATALISI approach was the explicit articulation of the visit's purpose. Unlike other peer-exchange formats (e.g. ERASMUS staff exchanges) that risk remaining generic, each Twinning in CATALISI was designed around a specific learning objective, namely the advancement of institutional transformation in a specific domain of intervention, identified through the prior matchmaking and needs' assessment process. This **clarity of purpose** enabled both hosts and visitors to prepare more effectively, ensured that discussions remained relevant to the Transformational Pathways, and maximised the value of the time spent on site.

At the same time, the Twinning format retained a high degree of **flexibility**. Interactive dialogue and informal exchanges allowed participants to move beyond the initial theme and touch upon interdependent areas of institutional change. Several visits revealed that even when a Twinning was centred on a single domain, the dynamic interaction naturally expanded the conversation toward related topics, leading to **unexpected consequences and new collaborations** emerging between HEIs. This balance between a focused agenda and the freedom to explore cross-cutting themes and opportunities was repeatedly cited by HEIs as a key enabler of meaningful and insightful exchanges.

- **Complementarity between host expertise and visitor needs:** the preliminary matchmaking exercise carried out by APRE proved effective. It ensured that hosts had expertise in the themes requested by visitors, and that visiting institutions came with articulated needs. This alignment increased the relevance of discussions and ensured that Twinning visits were highly targeted.

4.2.2. Benefits for HEIs' transformational pathways

The Twinning mechanism produced a set of benefits that complement, and in several cases deepen, those generated through the MML workshops:

- **Learning from concrete institutional practices:** where MMLs focused on collective reflection and co-creation, Twinning visits offered **hands-on insights** into how specific practices are implemented within host institutions. This enabled HEIs to identify

actionable solutions and assess the feasibility of transferring practices into their own contexts.

- **Better understanding of gaps and priorities:** the Twinning exchanges helped visiting institutions identify gaps, refine their internal priorities and connect observations with the strategic objectives defined in their Transformational Pathways.
- **Concrete takeaways:** many visits resulted in concrete takeaways such as templates, workflows, data practices, ethics procedures, engagement formats, editorial strategies or recognition & rewards models. These were valued as **reference frameworks** to be adapted internally. Several institutions indicated that Twinning outcomes would feed directly into the refinement of their Transformation Actions.
- **Building new collaborations:** different from MMLs, which brought all HEIs together, Twinning visits created strong bilateral or trilateral relationships that several institutions expressed interest in continuing (e.g., joint papers, CoARA work, future exchanges).

4.2.3. Limitations and Areas of improvements

Despite the overall success and positive feedback, the Twinning mechanism also highlighted areas where improvements are possible, especially regarding the following aspects:

- **Limited duration:** many institutions felt that one-day formats constrained the depth of discussion. Additional time for hands-on sessions, observation of workflows, or follow-up dialogues would further strengthen learning outcomes.
- **Need for more involvement of external actors:** although some Twinning visits engaged external experts (e.g., journal editors, ethics committee members), a greater involvement of such stakeholders could enrich the learning, especially on topics strongly embedded in national ecosystems.
- **Potential for more balanced participation across institutions:** in a few cases, visiting institutions could have benefited from broader internal representation (e.g., stronger involvement of researchers, administrative staff or management).
- **Need to institutionalise the Twinning mechanism and allocate dedicated funds:** institutions noted that sustaining this type of exchange beyond the project would require formal recognition within institutional strategies and dedicated financial resources to support staff mobility, preparation time and follow-up activities. Embedding the Twinning mechanism into long-term capacity-building plans was identified as a key condition for ensuring continuity, scalability and broader internal uptake.
- **Identification of a common output to consolidate learning:** the impact of Twinning visits could be further enhanced by agreeing on a shared post-visit output (e.g. a short joint reflection, a common position paper or a brief set of recommendations). Producing a concrete and co-created output would help solidify the knowledge exchanged, facilitate the internal dissemination of lessons learned and reinforce the collective understanding of good practices.

These recommendations for future improvements would further strengthen the Twinning approach and impact.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Within the CATALISI project, the implementation of the Twinning schemes, one of the three core learning activities of the acceleration service *“Reinforce Human Capital: Capacity Building & Outreach”*, has demonstrated the strategic relevance and added value of targeted peer-to-peer learning as a mechanism to foster and support institutional transformation in HEIs.

Through the organisation of **nine Twinning visits**, resulting in **22 staff exchange interactions**, the Twinning approach provided CATALISI implementers with a focused and practice-oriented setting to connect with peer institutions, observe concrete models and practices and engage in dialogue on specific areas requiring transformation. These exchanges enabled participants to deepen their understanding of institutional approaches, compare governance and implementation models and reflect on how concrete practices from other HEIs could inspire, inform or refine their own Transformational Pathways.

Taken together, the insights provided reaffirm that Twinning is not merely a project activity but a strategic approach to institutional capacity-building, capable of supporting universities as they navigate the complex reform processes. By complementing broader multi-stakeholder mechanisms such as the MML workshops with focused, practice-oriented exchanges, the Twinning schemes contribute to building institutional adaptability, strengthening human capital, and fostering a culture of continuous learning across CATALISI implementers.

More broadly, the CATALISI experience suggests a clear strategic recommendation emerging from the project: **purpose-driven mobility and peer-exchange formats**, such as Twinning and MML workshops, represent effective, widely used and replicable acceleration services for institutional transformation. Their **in-person nature** was consistently highlighted as a key strength, enabling direct observation of practices, deeper interaction and trust-building among participants. At the same time, grouping Twinning visits and MML workshops within a coherent framework allowed the consortium to maximise the benefits of face-to-face exchange while maintaining a balanced and resource-efficient approach.

While in-person exchanges clearly represent the most impactful format, the experience gained also indicates that elements of the Twinning methodology may be meaningfully adapted to **online or hybrid settings** when physical mobility is not feasible, albeit with reduced intensity. This flexibility further reinforces the value of Twinning as a **sustainable and replicable mechanism**, capable of being embedded into long-term institutional capacity building strategies and supporting HEIs as they implement complex reform processes required by the evolving European Research Area (ERA).

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APPENDIX A – QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE MATCHMAKING ANALYSIS

The table below illustrates the questions circulated among the CATALISI implementers to identify their needs and expertise regarding the Counselling (Wp3) and Twinning activities, and to support the subsequent matchmaking exercise and organisation of the exchanges.

<p>1</p>	<p>Please select the three priority intervention areas where you would need support and guidance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recognition of qualifications & research careers; • reform of research assessment; • digitisation of higher education sector; • supporting talent circulation/mobility; • accurately addressing lifelong learning; • strengthening of human capital; • gender equality and inclusiveness; • mainstreaming of Open Science; • public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges; • reinforcing the role of HEIs in local innovation ecosystems; • sharing of research infrastructures and capacities; • sustainability in education; • sustainability in research; • sustainability in campus operations.
<p>2</p>	<p>For the intervention areas that you prioritised (as indicated above), please specify the gap/issue that you would like to overcome. Please, provide us with a brief description.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>For each of the priority areas identified, could you indicate who (your team or other departments) could be a trainee for the implementation of the Twinning service.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Could you please select the intervention areas, where you as a university hold more knowledge/expertise, and where you could provide expertise in and guidance to other universities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recognition of qualifications & research careers; • reform of research assessment; • digitisation of higher education sector; • supporting talent circulation/mobility; • accurately addressing lifelong learning; • strengthening of human capital; • gender equality and inclusiveness; • mainstreaming of Open Science; • public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges; • reinforcing the role of HEIs in local innovation ecosystems; • sharing of research infrastructures and capacities; • sustainability in education; • sustainability in research; • sustainability in campus operations.

5	For the intervention areas where you hold more expertise in, could you please provide us with more details on the type of expertise (e.g. good practices, trainings, services, etc).
6	For the intervention areas where you hold more expertise in, could you indicate who (your team or other departments) could be identified as trainer?
7	Please enter your answer below if you have any additional comments.

APPENDIX B – TWINNINGS AGENDAS AND REPORTS

The individual Twinning Reports produced by host and visiting institutions following each Twinning visit are archived on the CATALISI project SharePoint and can be made available upon request. They are not fully annexed to this deliverable in compliance with privacy and GDPR requirements. Agendas only are included in this Appendix.

TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES AND PRACTICES AT KTU – 10/05/2024

Time	Description of activity	Host trainer(s)	Location (if onsite and/or Online)
09:30	Discussion "Open Science Policy and Data".	Audronė Telešienė, Giedrius Žvaliauskas	onsite Center for Data Analysis and Archiving (DATA Centre).
10:30	Discussion "Open Science and Research Ethics" Meeting with the members of University Research Ethics Committee.	Gintarė Tautkevičienė, Adriana Kviklienė Jurgita Duobienė	onsite KTU Central Library
13:00	Visit to KTU Campus Library. Guided tour and discussion "Infrastructure for Open Science Applications"	Gintarė Tautkevičienė	onsite KTU Campus Library
13:30	Visit to KTU interdisciplinary prototyping laboratory centre M-Lab. Guided tour and discussion "Infrastructure for Open Science Applications"	Lolita Jurkšienė	onsite KTU M-Lab
14:30	End of the Training Programme		

TWINNING ON RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY AT AUMC – 11/06/2024

Start time	Planned duration	Item description	Presenter
TWINNING AMSTERDAM UMC			

09:30	30 min	Welcome, coffee, expectations	
10:00	120 min	<p>Workshop on Research ethics</p> <p>Topics: Research Ethics Committees (REC); hot topics, issues and procedures</p> <p>Sharing insights and experiences with experts from on (non-medical) RECs</p>	<p>Mariëtte van den Hoven</p> <p>Joke Baas National Ethics Council for Social and Behavioural Sciences</p> <p>REC members</p>
12:00	90 min	CAMPUS TOUR + LUNCH	
14:00	60 min	<p>Workshop: Sharing insights from the Academic Integrity Committees in the Netherlands</p>	<p>Mariette van den Hoven & Rita Santos (coordinators Netherlands Research Integrity Network)</p> <p>Nathalie Trifkovic, RI coordinator of the VU</p>
15:00	60 min	<p>Research ethics and Research Integrity training; Interactive workshop sharing materials and assessment of training needs visiting partners</p>	<p>Miriam van Loon – trainings at Amsterdam UMC & VU iRECS Home – irecs</p> <p>Natalie Evans, Giulia Inguaggiato Embassy of Good Science</p>
16:00	15 min	Wrap up – lessons learned & ideas for future collaboration in CATALISI	
End of meeting			

TWINNING ON REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND ENGAGEMENT WITH LOCAL ECOSYSTEM AT LUISS – 18/10/2024

Start time	End time	Item description
10:00	10:45	Presentation of Internal Research Evaluation procedures (VIR) with Luiss Third Mission and Library staff
10:45	11:15	Open discussion about Research Assessment
11:15	11:45	COFFEE BREAK

11:45	12:00	Presentation about the use of Internal Research Evaluation (VIR) scores for the quality assessment of the Research Centres with Luiss Third Mission staff
12:00	12:30	Presentation on how external engagement is structured at the Luiss X.ITE Research Centre (focus on business development for commissioned research) with Professors working in the centre
12:30	13:00	Open discussion about Engagement with the Local Ecosystem
13:00	14:30	NETWORKING LIGHT LUNCH
14:30	16:30	Tour of the Luiss extended campus
16:30	End of meeting	

TWINNING ON public engagement and research careers at UCC – 13/11/2024

Time (GMT)	Description of activity	Host trainer(s)
November 13 th 10:30 - 11:00 (GMT)	Welcome and Orientation	All
11:00 - 12:00	Dialogue 1: Open Science and COARA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • David O'Connell (Director of Research Support Services), • Hardy Schwam (Head of Research Services, Library), • Aoife Coffey (Research Data Coordinator), • Donna O Doibhlin (Research Services, Library)
12:00 - 13:00	Dialogue 2: Third Mission and Societal Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ciara O'Halloran, (Programme Officer, Research Culture) • Martin Galvin (Head of Research Culture, Engagement and Impact), • David Hogan (Strategic Planning & Institutional Research)
	LUNCH	
14:00 – 15:00	Dialogue 3: Integrity and Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irene Kavanagh (Research Integrity Support Officer), • Aoife Coffey (Research Data Management Officer)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Ciara Heavin (PI and Chair of University Ethics Committee) • Ken O'Halloran (PI and Chair of Ethics Committee) • Christian Waeber (PI and Chair of UCC Animal Experimentation Ethical sub committee)
15:00 – 16:30	On site visits and meetings with staff/experts	As above
19:00	Optional Dinner at Market Lane	All

TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH AT KTU – 09/12/2024

Time	Description of activity	Host trainer(s)
10:00 - 10:30	Welcome coffee and introduction to the Twinning event	Egle Butkeviciene (KTU)
10:30 - 12:00	Sustainability in Research: Project Management System at KTU: Presentation and Discussion	Leonas Balasevicius (Director of Department of Research Affairs, KTU), Vilma Karobliene (Head of Research and Innovation Projects Centre, KTU)
12:00 - 13:00	Networking Lunch	All
13:00 - 14:30	Open Science and Open Data: data archives (Meeting at the Centre for Data Analysis and Archiving (DATA) Centre). Presentation and Discussion	Audrone Telesiene, Vaidas Morkevicius, Giedrius Zvaliauskas (Centre for Data Analysis and Archiving (DATA) Centre, KTU)
14:30 - 15:00	Coffee Break	All
15:00 - 16:30	Open Science and Research Ethics: Meeting with KTU Research Ethics Committee. Presentation and Discussion	Gintarė Tautkevičienė (Director of the KTU Library), Adriana Kviklienė (Head of the Research Activity Analytics Office)

TWINNING ON SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH AT AUTH – 23/01/2025

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
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09:30	10:00	Welcome & Overview: The Landscape of Research Funding in Greece	AUTH Team
10:20	10:50	Unlocking Funding Sources: Beyond EU Grants – From Idea to Grant and Sustained Impact Engaging Communities Through Open Citizen Science in EU projects: Opportunities and Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities as Platforms for Collaboration and Innovation Strategies for Building Long-Term Sustainability Beyond Initial Grant Funding 	TBC
10:50	11:30	Discussion with the visiting universities: Sustainability in Research Financing	TBC
11:30	11:40	COFFEE BREAK	
11:40	12:30	Funding Success Stories: From Idea to Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AUTH case studies of successful funded research projects, focusing on the key factors that led to their success and the lessons learned. 	
12:30	13:30	Interactive Discussion: Overcoming Common Challenges in Funding Participants share common challenges in securing and managing research funding, followed by group brainstorming on solutions and best practices.	
13:30	End of meeting – Light Lunch		

TWINNING ON RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND OPEN SCIENCE AT UJI – 03/04/2025

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
10:00	10:20	Introduction: The relevance of Open Access in contemporary science	Jesús Lancis, Vice-rector for research, UJI
10:20	10:50	Experiences of an Editor	Jorge Martí Contreras, Editor de <i>Cultura, Lenguaje y Representación</i> , UJI

10:50	11:10	Informal conversation with participants	
11:10	11:45	Researching Open Access (I) <i>The context of Spanish philosophy journals: An alternative structure to the commercial model</i>	Ramón Feenstra, ex-editor de <i>Recerca</i> . <i>Revista de Pensament</i> , UJI
11:45	12:00	Coffee Break	
12:00	13:00	Researching Open Access (II) <i>The context of journals in the field of communication sciences</i>	Jesús Segarra Saavedra, co-editor <i>Revista Mediterranea de Comunicacion</i> , Universitat d'Alacant
13:00	14:00	National and institutional Open Access initiatives: experiences from Netherlands	Natalie Evans and Rita Figueiras Alves dos Santos, AUMC
14:00	14:50	Luiss' steps towards Open Science	Evelina Praino and Chiara Annulli, Luiss
14:50	15:30	Informal conversation with participants	
15:30	End of meeting – Lunch		

TWINNING ON PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT TO SOLVE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES AT UG – 10/04/2025

Start time	Planned duration	Room	Item description	Presenter
09:00:09.15	15 min	C201	Morning coffee	
09.15:10.00	45 min	C209	Session focused on addressing the intervention area: <i>Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges</i> Presenting the actions for society Faculty of economics tour And talking about: Labs Student areas Experts council Other initiatives	Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz Przemysław Borkowski Dariusz Tłoczyński

10.00:10.30	30 min		Transfer to the main campus	
10.30:12.30	120 min	Library	<p><i>Session focused on intervention area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges, specifically open science practices</i></p> <p>Visit the Library</p> <p>Presenting open science initiatives and society-oriented initiatives</p> <p>Presenting the resources of the library</p> <p>Discussion on open science practices</p>	<p>Agnieszka Wasilewska</p> <p>Sala BUG</p>
12.30:13.30	60 min	Canteen	LUNCH	
13.30:15:30	120min	Fac. of Biology	<p><i>Session focused on intervention area: Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges</i></p> <p>Visit the mini-museum of amber</p> <p>Visit at the University Radio Mors studio</p> <p>Discussion of how to disseminate knowledge to a broad audience, how to use university resources to create open and accessible spaces for society use, how to convey the "university for society" idea</p>	<p>Sala BUG, Teams – dyskusja</p> <p>Monika Adamczuk</p>
15.30				

TWINNING ON OPEN SCIENCE AND RECOGNITION OF QUALIFICATION AND RESEARCH CAREERS AT AUMC – 15/05/2025

Start time	Planned duration	Item description	Presenter
15TH MAY 2025 – ELH DEPARTMENT			
Theme: recognition of qualifications and research careers			
14:00	10 min	Welcome	Prof. dr. Mariëtte vd Hoven

14:10	50min	Recognition & Rewards Program at the VU Amsterdam & Amsterdam UMC	Dr. Lieke van Fastenhout (VU Amsterdam) & Dr. Marjon van Wijnbergen (Amsterdam UMC)
15:00	45 min	Raising awareness for stimulating a positive research culture – initiatives from Amsterdam	Dr. Miriam van Loon, Dr. Rita F. Alves dos Santos
15:45	15 min	COFFEE BREAK	
16:00	60 min	Mapping recognition & rewards initiatives and challenges in each partner's institutions	All partners
17:00	End of meeting		
19:00	Dinner at Ode aan de Amstel Restaurant - link		

Start time	Planned duration	Item description	Presenter
16TH MAY 2025 – ELH DEPARTMENT			
Theme: mainstreaming of open science and impact and valorisation			
10:00	10 min	Welcome	Prof. dr. Mariëtte vd Hoven
10:10	30min	VU Amsterdam Open Science Program	Tycho Hofstra (VU Open Science Program)
10:40	30 min	Center for Research Integrity and Open Science (RIOS) mission and community engagement	Dr. Rita F. Alves dos Santos and Jack Fitzgerald
11:10	50 min	Research initiatives on Open Science and Reproducibility followed by roundtable discussion	Professor Mariska Leeflang (OSIRIS) Dr. Stefanie Meirmans (Replication in Action) Dr. Joeri Tjink & Ilse de Jonge (TRUSTParency) Dr. Sam Heijnen (Open Natural Data)
12:00	60 min	LUNCH	
13:00	30 min	VU Diamond Open Access journal – Philosophy of AI	Dr. Guido Löhr (Editor in Chief)

13:30	30 min	Impact and valorisation in the Humanities and Social Sciences	Dr. Maurijn de Heus (VU Research Office)
14:00	15 min	COFFEE BREAK	
14:15	45 min	Roundtable discussion on institutional strategies for research impact and valorisation	All partners
15:00	End of meeting		

APPENDIX C – TWINNING REPORTING TEMPLATE

1. General Information

Twinning University Host:

Twinning University Visiting:

Twinning Dates:

	Name	Role	Organisation name and country
Host Trainer(s)			
Visiting Trainees	1.		

2. Preparation process *(to be completed by Host Institution. Please, insert any internal organisation process, reflection meeting, etc).*

Date	Description	Participants

3. Activities and focus of the exchange *(to be completed prior to the Twinning and updated at the end of the exchange)*

Focus of the exchange (please indicate the main intervention area):

Insert agenda *(specify if the agenda was agreed with host institutions)*. Please specify the type of mentoring/training activities (e.g. seminar, onsite visit, workshop, meetings with staff/experts etc.).

Date and time	Description of activity	Host trainer(s)

NB: If you want to add columns with other information, feel free to do that.

4. Briefly report the activities performed and main outputs (*max. 200 words*).

5. Overall assessment (*to be completed at end of the Twinning by both Institutions*)

	Host Institution	Visiting Institution
1. What would you consider as the most helpful feature offered during this Twinning?		
2. What would you consider as (any) difficulties?		
3. What were the highlights and most important achievements/activities during this Twinning?		
4. Was the exchange useful for the advancement of your university's		

transformational pathway? How so?		
5. What was the most important learning outcome achieved from the exchange? How will you implement this knowledge in your organisation?		
6. What improvements and suggestions (if any) would you make for future twinning exchanges?		
7. Quality and appropriateness of Programme / agenda. Did the programme reflect your expectations?	NA	
8. Trainees contribution to programme / agenda, interaction with Assisting Trainer, Trainees active participation		NA

6. General Feedback on the Twinning service

- To what extent was the Twinning useful to secure knowledge and exchange best practices with your peers?
- Would you use this service in future and beyond the project to advance in the transformation of other intervention areas related to HEIs?

7. Follow-up materials

If any materials (e.g. the presentation slides, etc.) have been made public available, please specify where they can be found.